

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-10

QUALITY LEVEL OF ART EDUCATION

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A student of the 3rd stage of the field of study "Production in the field of art"

Abstract: The quality phase of art education aims to improve quality and ensure effective teaching in the art education process. At this stage, pedagogical methods, curricula, materials and student evaluation systems are analyzed. By improving the quality of art education, it is aimed to develop students' creativity, aesthetic sense and interest in art. In this process, it is important to share experience, introduce innovative methods and train qualified teachers.

Key words: Art education, quality, pedagogical methods, educational programs, assessment system, creativity, aesthetic development, innovative methods, exchange of experience, qualified teachers.

It is known that in 2005, the third qualitative stage of the "National Personnel Training Program" began in our country. Based on this law, a perspective plan for the development of the quality of art education until 2010 was drawn up in our institute. In it, the organization of educational work at the level of the requirements of the quality stage of the "National Personnel Training Program", inculcating the idea of national independence in students, improving educational standards and programs, providing educational subjects with literature, to speed up the publication of study guides and textbooks, to use new tools of spiritual and educational work, to further strengthen disciplinary work related to student participation in classes, to ensure the high efficiency of personnel training at the institute's graduate school, professor- huge tasks were defined, such as to further increase the scientific and creative potential of teachers, to consistently carry out the policy of rejuvenating the teaching staff by supporting talented young people. Fulfillment of such tasks created the basis for further improvement of the basic concept of the continuous education system in the field of art.

Since the development of art education is inextricably linked with spiritual and educational education, the ultimate goal is to carry them out in harmony.

At the heart of the spiritual and educational work carried out at the institute are the tasks of forming a mature generation loyal to the idea of national independence, bringing up young people with independent and free thinking, strong will, complete faith, loyal to their country, and loving to their people.

At the heart of these efforts, firstly, to build the educational system of the institute – education, scientific research and spiritual-educational work on the basis of the advice given by our honorable President when he visited our institute, as well as the relevant work of the head of our country deep study of his works; secondly, to widely involve all the leading professors and teachers of the institute in conveying the essence of the special subject "The idea of national independence: basic concepts and principles" to the minds of every student through the tools of their fields; In order to increase the efficiency of the "Spiritual Day" events, to carry out spiritual and educational activities in a comprehensive manner throughout the day, to educate them in the spirit of patriotism, self-sacrifice, to organize excursions to museums, historical and independence-era monuments in the capital and regions, concerts, take to theaters; fourthly, the high potential of the institute, the great contributions of professors and teachers to strengthening the independence of our country with their selfless work and achievements, and educating our people, especially the young generation, in the spirit of national

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and universal values through their personal examples, and the creativity of the leaders who have been awarded high titles by our government. wide promotion of activities; in addition to these, spiritual and educational events held at various levels, pageants, contests, competitions organized at the level of the republic, region, city, celebration of historical and holiday dates, debates and discussions on current topics with the relations of the republic and region appearances on television and radio, articles published in the periodical press form the basis of these activities.

As a result of the work carried out based on the above factors, the moral level of the students of the institute is improving. In this process, attention to moral values has increased, special attention is being paid to the fight against vices, their prevention, and warning students about the possible dire consequences. For this purpose, comprehensive measures are being implemented in cooperation with law enforcement, health, religious authorities and other relevant organizations. With their participation, practical conferences, meetings, and roundtable discussions have been organized. Also, students are taken en masse to films, plays, staged shows created on current topics. Therefore, opportunities for students and young people to meaningfully spend their free time from studying have increased. More than 10 different clubs, clubs, and sports sections operate in the institute. All material and household conditions have been created for them in the student accommodation. As it is impossible to imagine education without training, it is possible to achieve a comprehensively mature and well-rounded generation by harmonizing education and training in the institute, and by comprehensive systematization.

During the following years, serious changes are taking place in the educational and methodological process of the State Art Institute of Uzbekistan. All educational and methodological normative documents of bachelor's and master's degrees of higher education will be reworked based on global requirements.

Improving the educational process, students' mastery of subjects, requires careful teaching of specialized subjects. The educational, creative and scientific works prepared by the students of the specialized departments are developed due to their careful mastering of the secrets of the field.

Professors and teachers of the departments of the institute are actively involved in the preparation of model curricula and educational literature for secondary special, vocational colleges and academic lyceums in the field of art. The program and educational literature were prepared and submitted to the Higher Education Coordination Council of the Ministry of Higher Education for discussion.

Teaching of professors based on modern information and pedagogical technologies is under control. A lot of information related to educational-methodical, scientific-creative, organizational-structural areas implemented in the institute was prepared, presented to the information technology center of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, and posted on the website of the institute.

In order to bring the educational process closer to practice, the National Academic Drama Theater of Uzbekistan, the Opera and Ballet Theater named after Alisher Navoi, Drama Theater named after Abror Hidoyatov, Theaters of Youth and Young Audiences, Theaters of the Republic A close connection was established with puppet theater, "Ilhom" theater and other theaters in the republic. In addition to watching the works staged in them, our students also participate in the creation of such performances. This, in turn, serves to increase their skills.

The management of the institute plans to train art managers in order to prepare personnel who will respond to the conditions of the market economy.

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It will be possible to continuously improve the scientific and creative potential of professors and teachers. If in 1997 the scientific potential of professors and teachers of the institute was 29-30 percent, by now this indicator has exceeded 52 percent. In order to further increase the effectiveness of education, along with inviting highly qualified specialists from abroad, measures are also being taken to increase the scientific and creative potential of young teachers working at the institute through post-graduate studies and organization. In addition, the most talented masters who studied at the institute are being recruited to work in the departments, preparing the ground for the rejuvenation of the teaching staff.

Professors and teachers of the institute are conducting scientific research on art subjects on the basis of state grants. Currently, four topics have been submitted to the competition of innovation projects.

Complex studies are being conducted in the theoretical departments of the institute. As a result of the research carried out at the institute, textbooks and training manuals were created. For example: the teaching manual "Acting skills" by professors Jora Mahmudov and the multimedia "Stage battle" by Arsen Ismailov were duly awarded by taking pride of place in the Republican competition "The best training manual and textbook of the year". Active work is being done on the creation of multimedia and e-books. Two books prepared by the teachers of the institute were recognized as the best textbooks of the year.

In order to further improve the scientific potential, the materials of professor-teacher and student conferences, which are traditionally held every year, have been published. Since 2006, such materials have been published in the form of "Yilnoma". During these years, our professors and teachers participated in many national and international scientific-theoretical and creative-practical conferences, and their lectures were published as articles in foreign publications.

Since 2001, the newspaper "Kaldirgoch" has been regularly published in the institute in order to use the publishing works of students. Students of the Department of Art Studies and Journalism have been cooperating with a number of prestigious and popular newspapers of the republic.

In order to improve the scientific and creative qualifications of professors and teachers, they are sent to study at prestigious higher education institutions, professional development and retraining institutes in the republic and abroad, and "master-classes" of visiting experts from abroad are organized. In particular, the cooperation established with the Goethe Institute in Tashkent is giving good results in this regard. Noting that "Master-class" lessons have an important role for students in mastering specialized subjects, it is necessary to pay more attention to this aspect. The relations of professors and teachers of the institute with the countries of Independent Cooperation countries, which were temporarily interrupted, are being restored. In particular, the issue of establishing cooperation with the Moscow Academy of Arts and the National Academy of Arts of Kazakhstan was resolved. Recently, a group of students of the National Art Academy of Kazakhstan visited our institute. In the future, it is planned that the students of our institute will also conduct their internships in Almaty.

So, the political, socio-economic, and legal reforms carried out in our republic during the period of independence are reflected in all normative documents of art education and are implemented in the practice of the educational system of the institute. There is no doubt that the works carried out in order to further improve the quality of art education in the institute will make it possible to set more ambitious tasks in this field in the future and to fulfill them with dignity, and for this, ample opportunities are being mobilized.

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